

High-resolution experimental mapping of neutron flux in the BME Training Reactor

Ákos Csolti¹, András S. Ványi^{1,2}, Szabolcs Czifrus^{1,*}

¹Institute of Nuclear Techniques, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Műegyetem rkp. 3., H-1111 Budapest, Hungary;

²Institute for Atomic Energy Research, HUN-REN Centre for Energy Research, Konkoly-Thege út 29-33, H-1121 Budapest, Hungary

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803604

ABSTRACT

In frame of the Euratom project EVEREST, a series of high-resolution and high-precision measurements are performed to determine the spatial distribution of the neutron flux and moderator temperature in the BME Training Reactor, in order to provide validation data for multiphysics and Monte Carlo (MC) models. A neutron monitor activation campaign to map the spatial distribution of the neutron flux is being carried out. In frame of this, the authors plan to perform multiple foil activation measurements with various nuclear reactions such as $^{197}\text{Au}(n, \gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$, $^{115}\text{In}(n, \gamma)^{116}\text{In}$, $^{47}\text{Ti}(n, p)^{47}\text{Sc}$ etc. Of the planned measurements, the authors have already performed gold foil irradiations (1 wt% Au foils) at twenty in-core positions using four vertical carriers covering core center, edge and corner environments. The foil activities were measured with a HPGe detector, for which the absolute HPGe efficiency calibration was carried out with high-precision PTB standards. Saturation activities derived for each foil were compared to reaction rates obtained from Monte Carlo model calculations and consistent results were found. The dataset, to be amended in the near future with a large number of foil measurements, will help to establish a benchmark field for future validations.

Keywords: neutron flux measurement, activation monitors, training reactor, benchmark, simulation validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear reactor modeling increasingly relies on high-fidelity multiphysics and MC tools, yet credible model validation still depends on precise, well-documented experiments. Nevertheless, the number of benchmark-quality measurements in reactors where thermal feedback may be measurable is quite low.

In order to alleviate the situation, the authors initiated a measurement series for the core of the BME Training Reactor (TR) to determine the magnitude and spatial distribution of the neutron flux at a large number of in-core locations using the activation foil technique. Besides characterizing the irradiation field itself, the goal is to generate a high-resolution dataset for code validation within the EVEREST project [1].

As the Training Reactor has significant power to produce thermal feedback, extensive neutronic measurements on neutron flux values, temporal and spatial distributions, as well as temperature distributions inside the reactor vessel have been and will be performed. The authors have developed an experimental campaign that includes the measurement of the reaction rates of various activation detectors at numerous positions in the reactor core to establish a detailed activation-based benchmark. This paper presents the results of the irradiation of 20 bare gold foils that have already been performed and evaluated. The authors plan to measure further reaction rates of Cd covered $^{197}\text{Au}(n, \gamma)^{198}\text{Au}$,

*czifrus@reak.bme.hu

Figure 1. The core of the Training Reactor

$^{47}\text{Ti}(n, p)^{47}\text{Sc}$, and $^{27}\text{Al}(n, \alpha)^{24}\text{Na}$), while 10 to 12 different materials with various nuclear reactions such as $^{115}\text{In}(n, \gamma)^{116}\text{In}$, $^{58}\text{Ni}(n, p)^{58m}\text{Co}$ etc. are also to be irradiated at a few locations to obtain more extensive spectral information at these positions.

Gold activation is particularly suitable as a thermal neutron flux monitor because ^{197}Au has a well-known and low-uncertainty capture cross section and ^{198}Au has well-measurable decay signatures ($T_{1/2} = 2.695$ d, prominent 411.8 keV line).

In order to minimize measurement-related uncertainties, the monitor foils, their holders and the evaluation conditions are very precisely thought out and prepared. The activities of the neutron monitors are determined using a HPGe detector. In our approach, a consistent absolute HPGe calibration using 0.7% (2σ) PTB calibration sources and careful geometric reproducibility were as crucial as the in-core positioning strategy.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. The BME Training Reactor

The Training Reactor of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics is a light water moderated and cooled reactor of 100 kW nominal thermal power. The core consists of type EK-10 fuel assemblies, containing 10% enriched UO_2 in metal magnesium matrix. The fuel region is surrounded by graphite reflector assemblies (Fig. 1). The maximum thermal neutron flux in the reactor core is $2.7 \cdot 10^{12}$ n/(cm^2s).

The fuel, which was made in the 1960's in the former Soviet Union, has a total mass of 29.54 kg [2, 3]. The nominal pin pitch in the regular assemblies is 17 mm. Each fuel pin contains nominally 80 g uranium with the corresponding amount of oxygen and 13 g metal magnesium. The active length is 500 mm. The cladding of the fuel pin is 99.5% purity aluminum alloy, with an outer diameter and thickness of 10 mm and 1.5 mm, respectively. At each end of the fuel pins, there are inactive parts with a length of 45 mm.

2.2. Earlier measurements and simulations

The thermal neutron flux values in the pneumatic sample delivery system of the BME TR are routinely measured using gold foil activation during student exercises. Neutron spectrum measurements using the multiple-foil techniques have also been carried out [4]. Starting from the 2000s, fine-detail deterministic and MCNP simulations were performed for the reactor core, for which validation experiments were required. However, the age-related uncertainties of the reactor (e.g. lack of detailed fuel specifications, loss of knowledge regarding reactor construction) made it difficult to set up precise models. Therefore, staff of the BME Institute of Nuclear Techniques set up a research group to clarify details and elaborate a reference document [3]. Later, in frame of a PhD work [2], Serpent and PARCS models were also prepared based on the reference document [5]. This was also followed by a thermal-hydraulics [6] and a coupled model [7]. An experimental modelling program was also started using the PIV laboratory of the Institute [8], focusing on the natural circulation occurring in the full-size electronically heated mock-up of the EK-10 fuel assembly, in order to deepen our understanding of the thermal-hydraulics phenomena that occur in the reactor.

2.3. Uncertainties

In order to further reduce the uncertainties primarily associated with the relatively poor knowledge about the fuel, a series of characterization measurements have been initiated for a spare fuel assembly. In this project, the fuel pins of the assembly were removed and individually analyzed. Physical characteristics determined include the length, diameter, and mass, while the distribution of these quantities is also determined. Furthermore, x-ray and ultrasound measurements were also performed to understand the accurate length and diameter of the active part of the fuel. As a cut fuel pin piece was also available, an ICP-MS analysis was also performed to determine the uranium content and enrichment of the fuel. Further measurements are planned, such as gamma-spectroscopy analysis.

3. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

3.1. HPGe detector absolute efficiency calibration and measurement setup

The authors calibrated the full-energy peak efficiency $\varepsilon_p(E)$ of a Canberra HPGe detector with PTB-certified ^{60}Co , ^{54}Mn , ^{137}Cs and ^{133}Ba sources referenced to a common date, for which the manufacturer quoted 0.7% activity uncertainty at $k = 2$ level. Decay corrections were applied to compute activities at the time of calibration. The fitted $\varepsilon_p(E)$ curve (Fig. 2) reproduces measured points within approximately 2% over 50–1400 keV; the 411.8 keV efficiency used for ^{198}Au activity measurement is $\varepsilon_p(411.8 \text{ keV}) = 1.30 \cdot 10^{-3}$. Parameter uncertainties from the fit and source certificates were propagated to each derived activity. Taking all these into account, 1.55% relative uncertainty was obtained for $\varepsilon_p(411.8 \text{ keV})$.

Counting was performed in a low-background shielded chamber (Pb/Cu graded shielding) with the HPGe endcap fixed relative to a stack of plastic spacers. A dedicated thin-bottom sample cup seats into the upper spacer so that the foil-to-detector geometry during counting replicates that used for absolute efficiency calibration. Peaks were integrated with GENIE-type analysis software; dead time was held well below 5% for the counts.

3.2. Foil material and sample holders

Monitor foils were 1 wt% Au in Al ($\varnothing = 5$ mm diameter, thickness of 0.2 mm). The light dilution suppresses self-shielding in gold; at this thickness/geometry, self-absorption corrections are negligible. Foils were cleaned in alcohol, air-dried, weighed three times on an officially calibrated microbalance (0.01 mg resolution) and sealed in thin polyethylene sachets (Fig. 3) that were previously verified not to introduce measurable attenuation or activation artifacts.

Figure 2. Measured efficiency values and the fitted efficiency-energy curve

Figure 3. Monitor foils in thin polyethylene sachets

Figure 4. Plexiglass sample holders with metal elements mounted at the end, ensuring the reproducible positioning of the samples

The carriers are assembled from threaded clear acrylic (PMMA or plexiglass) elements (Fig. 4); pockets for foils are realized as shallow cylindrical cavities at well-defined depths from the top alignment plane. The length of the sample holder rods is identical to that of the fuel rods, and each contains five cavities suitable for accommodating the samples. Mechanical stops ensured reproducible positioning, by seating on top of the fuel element spacer grid.

3.3. In-core positioning and irradiation

The fuel lattice of the Training Reactor has a square configuration, and the cylindrical sample holders were placed in the subchannels between the fuel rods. Different in-core lattice positions were chosen to sample representative neutron environments with varying spectral and moderation conditions: E6 (near the core center), B5 (intermediate position near core edge), E3 ("regular" edge, close to F3 with water irradiation channel), and F7 (corner adjacent to water/graphite reflectors). The selected irradiation positions are shown in Fig. 5. Each location received one carrier containing five foils, nominally placed at evenly spaced axial positions along the active fuel length, enabling the reconstruction of axial profiles.

All irradiations were conducted at nominal 10 kW steady power. The nominal displayed power is based on gold foil measurement that inherited the legacy power calibration of the 1970s. The power history was tightly controlled; individual irradiations lasted 1200 s (20 min) to reach a large but manageable activity for high-precision counting without excessive dead time.

Figure 5. The selected sample holder positions are marked with red Xs on the core map

3.4. Evaluation of monitor foils

For each foil, the end of irradiation (EOI) time, removal time, and counting start/stop were recorded to form accurate cooling and live times. In order to achieve higher data accuracy, exact integration of the decaying count rate was applied over the live time interval. For each spectrum, the net full-energy peak area at 411.8 keV was obtained by background-subtracted fitting. The saturation activity per target nucleus (“per-atom A_{sat} ”) was back-calculated. Typical short counts (≈ 10 – 20 min live time) yielded net peak areas ranging from $1.2 \cdot 10^4$ to $8.5 \cdot 10^4$ counts for most foils, corresponding to EOI activities of tens of kBq. Two foils were counted overnight to reduce statistical uncertainty below 0.15% in the peak area, serving as internal consistency checks.

The EOI activities can be calculated using Eq. 1, based on the cooling and measurement times (t_{cool} and t_{live} , respectively), the net counts in the full-energy peak (I_N), the decay constant (λ), the absolute γ intensity (k) and the detector efficiency corresponding to the given geometry and energy ($\varepsilon_p(E)$).

$$A_0(\tau) = \frac{\lambda I_N}{\varepsilon_p(E)k(1 - e^{-\lambda t_{live}})e^{-\lambda t_{cool}}} \quad (1)$$

The EOI activity values after an irradiation time of τ can be described by the relation given in Eq. 2, where A_{sat} is the saturation activity per target nucleus, and N is the number of ^{197}Au nuclei in the given foil sample.

$$A_0(\tau) = A_{sat}N(1 - e^{-\lambda\tau}) \quad (2)$$

For calculating the uncertainties, standard Gaussian error propagation was adopted. Components in

the uncertainty budget include peak-area counting statistics, $\varepsilon_p(E)$ calibration uncertainty, weighing uncertainty, and geometric reproducibility.

The saturation activities (A_{sat}) and relative uncertainties ($\sigma_{A_{sat}}^{rel}$) are shown in Table I.

Table I. Measured saturation activities and relative uncertainties

Sample	A_{sat} [1/s]	$\sigma_{A_{sat}}^{rel}$ [%]	Sample	A_{sat} [1/s]	$\sigma_{A_{sat}}^{rel}$ [%]
1	$1.706 \cdot 10^{-11}$	1.97	11	$1.052 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.08
2	$2.992 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.09	12	$1.781 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.11
3	$3.639 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.13	13	$2.203 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.11
4	$3.039 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.09	14	$1.946 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.09
5	$1.739 \cdot 10^{-11}$	1.96	15	$1.044 \cdot 10^{-11}$	1.93
6	$1.999 \cdot 10^{-11}$	1.97	16	$2.386 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.13
7	$3.740 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.09	17	$4.233 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.03
8	$4.750 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.10	18	$5.373 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.03
9	$4.180 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.07	19	$4.829 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.09
10	$2.382 \cdot 10^{-11}$	1.93	20	$2.582 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.09

The positions of the plexiglass carriers and the samples contained in them during the irradiation are shown in Table II. In each series, the first listed sample was positioned at the top of the sample holder (and thus at the uppermost position in the reactor core), while the subsequent samples were placed progressively lower.

Table II. The positions of the sample holder rods within the reactor core and the samples irradiated in them

Sample holder	Position	Samples
I	E3	1, 2, 3, 4, 5
II	B5	6, 7, 8, 9, 10
III	F7	11, 12, 13, 14, 15
IV	E6	16, 17, 18, 19, 20

4. SIMULATIONS

Over the years, high-precision Monte Carlo models of the BME Training Reactor have been developed at the Institute of Nuclear Techniques using the well-known MCNP, Serpent and OpenMC codes. In the framework of the EVEREST project, collaborations are on-going with other European institutes to further develop these models and to leverage the reaction rate measurements. Besides the use of MC codes, multiphysics models are also elaborated to accurately account for thermal feedback phenomena. To simulate the measurements presented in this paper, the MCNP code (version 6.3) was chosen. The used model (version 4.2.15) was based on the description [3]. The geometry was only slightly modified to incorporate the four plexiglass sample carriers described in Section 3 and to reflect the control rod positions during the irradiations. To estimate the reaction rates corresponding to the measurements, type F4 tallies were defined in each air filled 3.6 mm radii, 8 mm high cylindrical foil positioning volume. Also, type FM4 multipliers were defined, which set the power normalization and the gold (n, γ) reaction to be tallied. The calculations were carried out utilizing the ENDF71x ACE library (specifically, .80c extensions that are evaluated at 293.6 K), which is entirely based on the ENDF/B-VII.1 cross-section library. The simulations were performed in KCODE mode, with 50000 active cycles, each carried out with 100000 source neutrons.

5. DISCUSSION

The performed MC simulations were normalized to the nominal reactor power of 10 kW assuming that a total of 202.27 MeV of energy is deposited per fission (this is the default value in the Serpent MC code). A more thorough Monte Carlo analysis of this energy released per fission is among the tasks to be carried out during the evaluation of the planned experimental campaign. Fig. 6 presents the obtained simulated reaction rates compared with the corresponding measured values. To quantify the expected and observed linear relationship between the calculated and experimental values, unconstrained linear regression and zero-intercept linear fit were performed on the data points.

Figure 6. C/E comparison of the calculated and measured reaction rates. The plot includes two linear fits on the data points ($R^2 = 0.98$ in both cases).

It can be observed that the data shown in Fig. 6 exhibit good agreement with both fitted lines. However, the slope of the lines is considerably smaller than unity, which suggests a normalization related issue. Indeed, it has been reported that the nominal and physical power of the BME reactor might significantly differ [2]. One of the expected outcomes of the measurement series presented in this paper is to provide a new state-of-the-art calibration of the reactor power. To achieve this, in addition to the various additional foil activation measurements, precise coupled neutron-photon transport simulations will be performed to better quantify the energy deposition in the reactor.

Regarding the uncertainties, in the case of the measurements, the dominant sources taken into account come from the detector efficiency ($\approx 1.5\%$ at 412 keV) and the counting statistics for the peak areas (0.3–0.9%). On the other hand, the considered simulation uncertainties ($\approx 1\%$) are only related to the Monte Carlo statistics. The quantification of further uncertainties associated to the utilized nuclear library, the geometric positioning of the samples and the used power calibration are beyond the scope of this paper and are not therefore rigorously accounted for.

Future experimental campaigns will reduce geometric uncertainties by replacing acrylic carriers (which exhibited visible radiation yellowing) with radiation-hard fixtures and by adding cadmium-covered gold foils to isolate the epithermal contribution directly.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, a precise foil-activation methodology is presented for measuring the spatial distribution of thermal neutron flux in 20 core positions in the BME Training Reactor at a nominal power of 10 kW. The absolute efficiency calibration and live-time treatment of the applied HPGe detector support sub-percent counting precision. The derived saturation activities reliably normalize and validate the corresponding Monte Carlo reaction rate predictions. After the addition of similar irradiations, the resulting measured thermal flux distribution will form the basis of an EVEREST benchmark irradiation field.

Near-term continuation will extend the monitor set to include cadmium-covered gold foils, additional threshold foils (Al, Ti, Fe) to map other constituents of the neutron spectrum, and more measurement locations to intensify lateral sampling around control elements. Based on the entire set of measurements, a new power calibration of the I&C system of the Training Reactor will be performed in frame of the upcoming Periodic Safety Review.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project EVEREST is financially supported by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101163288.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Périn, M. Hursin, N. Garcia-Herranz, K. Ambrozic, and S. Czifrus. "The EVEREST Project: Toward Experimental Validation of Advanced Multi-Physics Tools for Fluence Source Term Calculation." In *Proceedings of the PHYSOR-2026*. American Nuclear Society (2026).
- [2] A. S. Ványi. *Experimental and numerical multi-physics analysis for the BME Training Reactor*. Phd dissertation, Budapest University of Technology and Economics (2023).
- [3] G. Klujber and A. Horváth. "Benchmark description of the BME Training Reactor." Technical Report BME-NTI-854/2018 (version 3.0), Institute of Nuclear Techniques, Budapest University of Technology and Economics (2020).
- [4] E. M. Zsolnay and E. J. Szondi. "Neutron spectrum determination by multiple foil activation method." *Periodica Polytechnica Electrical Engineering*, **volume 26**(1-2), pp. 31–46 (1982).
- [5] A. S. Ványi, B. Babcsány, Z. I. Böröczki, A. Horváth, M. Hursin, M. Szieberth, and S. Czifrus. "Steady-state neutronic measurements and comprehensive numerical analysis for the BME training reactor." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 155**, p. 108144 (2021).
- [6] A. S. Ványi, M. Hursin, A. Aszódi, L. Adorján, B. Biró, B. Magyar, P. Mészáros, T. Bozsó, and S. Czifrus. "Thermal-hydraulic measurements and TRACE system code analysis performed on the natural circulation cooled BME Training Reactor." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 189**, p. 109839 (2023).
- [7] A. S. Ványi, M. Hursin, and S. Czifrus. "Analysis of transient measurements with thermal feedback and coupled TRACE/PARCS calculations performed on the BME Training Reactor." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 194**, p. 110072 (2023).
- [8] G. I. Orosz, L. Schaul, B. B. Mészáros, D. Kacz, and A. Aszódi. "PIV measurements of natural circulation driven flow inside and around SMR fuel assemblies." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 445**, p. 114475 (2025).